

Teaching Students to Work With Pedagogical Situations in the Teaching of Pedagogical Disciplines

Durdona Aktamovna Akhatova

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor Department of General Pedagogy and Psychology Navoi State Pedagogical Institute,

ABSTRACT: The article is devoted to the issue of teaching students to work with pedagogical situations when teaching pedagogical disciplines in higher education. The literature on this topic is commented on. The article argues the relevance of teaching students to work with pedagogical situations in modern conditions. The level of development of the topic is analyzed in detail, the priorities of the development of pedagogical science, its role and importance in higher education are discussed. The focus is on innovative educational technologies and pedagogical situations used in the teaching of pedagogical disciplines, as well as the situation, the essence of the pedagogical situation. Opinions are expressed on finding positive solutions to the problems of the pedagogical situation. There are examples of pedagogical ministries used in the form of cases and methods of finding solutions. Conclusions and recommendations were made on the topic. The list of used literature is given.

KEYWORDS: pedagogy, students, higher education, training, pedagogical technology, innovation, interactive methods, problem-based learning, interactive learning, situation, pedagogical situation, situational problem, Keys, "Case-study".

INTRODUCTION

Article 36 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", approved on September 23, 2020, is entitled "Experimental and innovative activities in the field of education" and states: "Experimental and innovative activities in the field of education are aimed at modernizing education and developing new educational technologies and resources, testing them and introducing them into the educational process" [1].

And we do this through innovation in education. One of the significant requirements for teachers and educators is to teach young people to think independently through a deep understanding and application of innovation in education. One of the most pressing problems facing the education system is the development of practical foundations for the use of modern pedagogical and innovative technologies in the organization of the educational process and effective ways of using them.

Achieving educational effectiveness through the introduction of modern pedagogical and innovative technologies into the entire education system, including the teaching of pedagogical disciplines, remains one of the most important requirements of today. Based on this requirement, a number of measures are being taken to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions, to modernize the educational process, to develop the professional competence of teachers in improving the quality of the training system. Based on this requirement, we have prepared an article on teaching students to work with pedagogical situations in the teaching of general pedagogy.

The level of elaboration of the theme. At the current stage of our society, many of our scientists are making a worthy contribution to the development of pedagogy. In particular, such scientists as A.Munavvarov, R.Mavlonova [10], J.Hasanbaev, B.Khodkhayev [16] have created a number of textbooks and manuals on pedagogy.

B.L.Farberman [8], N.S.Saidakhmedov [15], M.Ochilov [14], M.Mahmudov [11], N.I.Azizkhodjayeva [3] and others were among the first pedagogical scientists to introduce pedagogical technology in the educational process and its recognition as a science in the republic. Our scientists J.G. Yuldashev, B. Khodjayev, N. Muslimov, R. Ishmuhamedov have extensively studied pedagogical innovations and technologies, modular approaches to teaching and interactive methods.

Teaching Students to Work With Pedagogical Situations in the Teaching of Pedagogical Disciplines

The experience of preparing teachers for innovative activities is generalized in the scientific and pedagogical literature (L.S. Podimova, T.K. Klimenko, V.F. Lechtman, etc.). Russian scientists A.I. Prigogin, B.V. Sazonov, V.S. Tolstoy, N.P. Stepanov focused on the study of the innovation process and its components [13].

THE MAIN PART

The 21st century will be an age of intelligence, spirituality and knowledge. That is why this century requires radical changes in the socio-economic, spiritual and educational development of society. These radical changes are primarily aimed at educating young people to form a harmoniously developed generation. The science of pedagogy has a special place in the implementation of these tasks. It is very difficult to move a society forward without the achievements of pedagogy.

Approaching the issue from this point of view, this social order, which is set before the educational institutions of the republic, especially the higher education institutions engaged in the training of specialists, provides innovative pedagogical training for future teachers-educators studying in higher education. It is obvious that it is important to get acquainted with the essence and content of technologies, to equip them with practical skills and abilities to apply them in practice.

Therefore, at the same time, it is necessary to provide future teachers with an understanding of the theoretical and practical foundations of innovative technologies, the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies in interactive methods and their application. Classes based on pedagogical technology satisfy the desire of young people to express their views on important life achievements and problems, give them the opportunity to think, to justify their views.

Pedagogical technologies used in higher education:

- problem-based learning;
- technologies that develop critical thinking;
- developmental educational technologies;
- game technologies;
- differentiated and individualized teaching technology;
- programmed learning technology;
- computer and information technologies.

The best way to increase the effectiveness of teaching general pedagogy is to organize classes using innovative pedagogical and information technologies and interactive methods [5].

Interactive education (English – “interact”, Russian – “interactive”; “inter” - interaction, “act” - action) - the development of students’ knowledge, skills, abilities and certain moral qualities education based on the organization of interaction in the language.

The role of problematic situations and educational tasks in the field of pedagogy is invaluable in the preparation of students for responsible work, involving them in the independent acquisition of knowledge, creative research, teaching and research activities.

A situation is a process in which a person perceives the beginning of a set of events and the transition to life conditions and situations that open up to his or her activities. **The pedagogical situation** is a fact of life, a fact that the educator encounters in his daily life and raises pedagogical issues that need to be addressed. While some types of common pedagogical situations allow students to quickly express, solve, and overcome pedagogical problems in the process of analyzing student behavior, other less common types of situations are complex, unique, and self-sufficient. It can be time consuming and sometimes completely unresolved situations.

The solution to many situational problems involves the analysis of specific situations that reflect changes in society. These situations can be new not only to the student but also to the teacher and in turn change the nature of the relationship between teacher and student. In traditional teaching practice, the teacher knows, and the student does not know. In solving situational problems, the teacher and the student act as equal partners in learning to solve the problem together. Thus, in solving situational problems, the teacher emerges not as a source of correct answers, but as a person who “helps” the student, leading to a change in the teacher-student relationship in the educational process.

The process of solving situational problems always involves the student “going” beyond the boundaries of the learning process, into the space of social practice. In other words, in such a process, conditions are created for students to enter into active team activities. The active participation of students provides an opportunity to develop practical competencies - basic skills, competencies and readiness to act. Problem situations and learning tasks allow students not only to gain independent knowledge, thinking, problem-solving experience, but also to discuss together the information they have collected on each topic

Teaching Students to Work With Pedagogical Situations in the Teaching of Pedagogical Disciplines

of the pedagogical course, to digest the critical ideas expressed in it with gratitude. The culture of doing and drawing the right conclusions from them, the solution that is found to be optimal, forms a complex skill that sometimes requires patience, courage, such as bringing the whole group to the course discussion.

Most importantly, problem situations and learning tasks can be used as part of problem-based learning when certain conditions are created. Therefore, when discussing with students a variety of problem situations and learning tasks, it is necessary to teach future teachers the general methods and techniques of finding their solution, to raise students to a higher level of mental development, as well as in the classroom. It is necessary to try to select systems that allow to reduce the amount of knowledge imparted by the teacher as much as possible. This is an important feature of problem-based learning.

Problem situations and learning assignments usually require teacher guidance. This is manifested in the selection of problem situations and learning tasks that are discussed in the first place.

From the above it is clear that the pedagogical fact, the analysis of events, the correct assessment of the specific situation of future teachers, finding appropriate methods and techniques of education, the theoretical issues of pedagogy, the activities of teachers and students armed with skills such as bonding. For students to be able to find solutions to pedagogical situations:

- Students are introduced to pedagogical situations of different content;
- They will be given the opportunity to observe the presented pedagogical situation;
- Listening to the personal views of a particular student on **finding positive solutions to pedagogical situations**, assessing in the classroom the correctness of the solution of the situation.

He suggested that students rely on the ideas of L.V. Zanina and N.P. Menshikova [19] in finding solutions to pedagogical situations. They are in the process:

- first put forward a number of hypotheses that will help to find a solution to the pedagogical situation;
- determine the direction of action, types of activities, pedagogical influence or methods of education;
- predict their effectiveness;
- Development of several options for action aimed at finding a solution;
- choose effective methods;
- Recommend that they determine the appropriate organizational forms.

Pedagogical ministries are often used in the form of cases. Depending on the specific objectives of the training, the cases are very different in terms of the content and organization of the material presented to them: cases of teaching analysis and evaluation; problem-solving and decision-making cases; there may be cases that represent a problem, a solution, or a concept in general.

Keys — is a written description of some specific real situation in an organization. During its use, students are asked to analyze the situation, consider the nature of the problem, suggest possible options, and choose the most appropriate one. The main purpose of the “case-study” is to strengthen students’ knowledge of the practical use of conceptual schemes and models in solving various situations, including pedagogical situations, as well as the development of skills of group analysis and decision-making consists of.

The teacher can play an “active” or “passive” role in the analysis of learning situations. At times, he “conducts” the analysis, and at other times he concludes the discussion. Seeing a great way to prove it, supporting it, or even taking others out of the discussion, is determined to make that path a priority. “Analyzing the case in class, I usually tell them which solution I think is right, and then I ask the students to find a blank side of my point of view. It helps them develop a personal approach to the problem,” said Peter Ekman [2, 8].

Here is an example of a case study used in teaching the module of general pedagogy “Educational and ethical views in the pedagogical pedagogy of the East”.

KEYS

1. Statement of Keys (problem).

Mahmud Kashgari’s *Diwān Lughāt al-Turk* is a collection of poems written between 1076 and 1077 and written as advice to young people. The songs on the devon reflect nature, hunting and battle scenes, love and admonition.

There are many poems in the poems that promote the value of knowledge, respect for educated people, hospitality, kindness, courage and bravery, greed, greed, betrayal of friends and people.

Teaching Students to Work With Pedagogical Situations in the Teaching of Pedagogical Disciplines

The main purpose of the sermon is to encourage the acquisition of knowledge and to promote its benefits. There are many educational articles.

Why is this work considered an encyclopedia of its time? Isn't it just dictionaries?

2. Keys assignment or question.

1. In your opinion, what is the reason for evaluating *Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk* as an encyclopedia?
2. Justify the educational aspect of the work

3. Resources to use.

1. Hashimov K., Nishonova S. History of pedagogy. - T.: National Library of Uzbekistan Publishing House, 2005.
2. Hoshimov K., C.Ochil. Anthology of Uzbek pedagogy. - T.: Teacher, 1999.
3. Majmud Kashqari's work "*Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk*"

4. Guidelines for students.

Stages of work	Tips and tricks .
1. Get acquainted (gain, obtain) with Keys and his information	Get acquainted with the case first. Get acquainted with the educational and moral works of the Eastern Renaissance, as well as Mahmud Kashgari's " <i>Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk</i> ". Do not rush to analyze the situation while reading
2. Get acquainted with the given situation	Please read the case information carefully again. Highlight the lines that matter to you. Underline the key points in the case with a pencil. Focus on the key concepts and phrases given in the situation description. Imagine the time when Mahmoud Kashgari lived. Read " <i>Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk</i> "
3. Problem situation analysis	Focus on the main problem and the minor problems . <i>The main problem: what educational and moral ideas are put forward in "<i>Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk</i>" ?</i> Try to answer the following questions. 1. What is the main idea of the work? 2. Note the disciplines in which the work contributed . 3. Give examples of his encyclopedic work.
4. Selection and justification of methods and means of solving the problem situation	To find the answers to these questions, go to the "Problem Situation" table below. To solve the problem, consider all the situations and create an alternative situation. Choose the solution to the problem from the specific options, find the exact solution to the problem. Fill in the table. Attach the results of working with cases in writing

Problem analysis and solution table

Evidence to support the problem	Causes of the problem	The solution proposed by the author	Group solution

Finish the work and prepare for the presentation.

5. Teacher (caseologist) solution

M. Kashgari's "*Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk*", Yusuf Khos Hajib's "*Qutadgu bilig*", Ahmad Yugnaki's "*Hibbatul haqoyiq*" written in the X-XII centuries are the common literary heritage of all Turkic peoples. It is known that Mahmud Kashgari's "*Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk*" is not only a dictionary, ie an Arabic translation of his words, but also contains examples of literature of the pre-Arab period. is also a wonderful work of art. Because it contains many proverbs, wise sayings, songs, phrases, fragments of epics about the folklore. About 6,000 Turkish words have Arabic explanations. The book also provides information on the history, ethnography, socio-economic status and other aspects of many Turkic tribes and clans. In this sense, the work has risen to the level of an encyclopedia of its time. In the history of world science and culture, "*Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk*" was of great importance as the first example of such works. Because no one in the history of the world had ever studied languages by comparison.

Teaching Students to Work With Pedagogical Situations in the Teaching of Pedagogical Disciplines

Mahmud Kashqari collected a great deal of material in writing this work. He examined the language of the Turkic peoples living in the area from East Turkestan to the shores of the Caspian Sea.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In modern conditions, the quality and effective organization of education and upbringing is on the agenda as a social necessity. Meeting this need requires educators to have a high level of professional competence, skills and competencies. Educators creative approaches to the educational process stimulate students' interest in learning and help them to intensify their learning activities. In addition, it creates the necessary conditions for students to actively master the creative qualities, creative abilities and skills as a specialist.

The use of innovative technologies, interactive methods and pedagogical situations in teaching general pedagogy also contributes to an increase in the activity of students, the formation of their creative abilities, pedagogical skills, and pedagogical creativity.

Prospective teachers need to be taught to think creatively, to adapt to changing situations, to organize activities on the basis of free competition, and to ensure that they use information technology, e-textbooks, versions and multimedia in their lessons. This requires students to develop independence, free thinking, analysis of academic performance, and, in the future, professional skills and computer literacy to become their internal needs.

Suggestions and recommendations on the topic:

- Development of a system of innovative technologies and interactive methods that contribute to the effectiveness of teaching the subject "General Pedagogy";
- Development of a technological map of each module, a set of practical developments and cases, guidelines for control tasks and independent learning in accordance with the requirements of innovative pedagogical and information technologies for the didactic support of teaching pedagogical disciplines;
- Appropriate use of educational opportunities of technology and interactive methods in teaching science;
- It is necessary to develop methodological recommendations for the use of innovative pedagogical and information technologies in the teaching of pedagogical modules and on this basis to develop a full didactic support for teaching the subject "General Pedagogy" based on the use of innovative pedagogical and information technologies.

REFERENCES

- 1) Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" No. ZRU-637, adopted on September 23, 2020.
- 2) Abdukodirov AA Cases from the disciplines "Pedagogy" and "Psychology" and methods of their use. –Tashkent: "Science and Technology" 2015. –p. 161.
- 3) Azizkhodjaeva N.I. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills, Tashkent: 2003
- 4) Akhatova Durdon A. Aktamovna, Akhatova Khilola Aktamovna. The essence and structure of the formation of Deontological Culture in future Teachers. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, VOLUME 10 March 2021
- 5) Axatova Durdon A. Aktamovna. Axatova Hilola Aktamovna MODERN PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. Vol. 8 No. 3, 2020 ISSN 2056-5852. Page 182-188
- 6) Ahatova Durdon A. Aktamovna, Khodjjeva Farogat Oltievna. The Actuality And The Content Of Forming Critical Thinking Skills Of Primary School Pupils. PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION (2020) 57(8):, 555-563
- 7) Akhatova D.A., Akhatova Kh.A PHENOMENON OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN PEDAGOGY. SCIENCE AND WORLD International scientific journal, № 1 (77), 2020, Vol. II, 21-23
- 8) Farberman B.L. Progressive pedagogical technologies Tashkent: 1999 –p. 84; Modern methods of teaching in higher education institutions", Tashkent: 2002; "Advanced pedagogical technologies", Tashkent: 2000),
- 9) Ishmuhamedov R.J., M.Mirsolieva. Innovative educational technologies in the learning process. Tashkent: «Science and technology», 2014. –p. 60.
- 10) Mavlonova R. et al. Pedagogy. (For secondary special educational institutions) Tashkent: 2008
- 11) Mahmudov M .. Didactic design of education, Tashkent: 2001
- 12) Muslimov N.A. and others. Innovative educational technologies. Educational-methodical manual. Tashkent: "Sano-standart", 2015. –p. 208.

Teaching Students to Work With Pedagogical Situations in the Teaching of Pedagogical Disciplines

- 13) N.A.Muslimov.M.H.Usmonboeva. Educational-methodical complex on the module “Innovative educational technologies and pedagogical competence”. Network Center for Retraining and Advanced Training of Teachers at Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami. Tashkent: 2017, -p. 42.
- 14) Ochilov M. New pedagogical technologies. Karshi: “Nasaf”, 2000
- 15) Sayidaxmedov N.S. Pedagogical skills and pedagogical technology. Tashkent: 2003; New pedagogical technologies: Theory and practice, Tashkent: “Finance”, 2003
- 16) Khodjayev BH General pedagogical theory and practice. Textbook. Tashkent: SANO-STANDARD, 2017
- 17) Hoshimov K., Nishonova S. History of pedagogy. Textbook, Tashkent: 2005,217 p
- 18) Yusuf Khos Khojib. Qutadgu bilig (foreword by B.Tuxliev). Tashkent: Yulduzcha, 1991.
- 19) <http://bimm.uz> – The main scientific and methodological center for the organization of retraining and advanced training of teachers and managers of the higher education system. BIMM. Distance learning platform. Basics module of creative pedagogy. 2020, November, -p. 18